

Human reaction modeling for collaborative robotic applications in virtual environment

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Abstract—Model-based approaches aiming to characterize human behavior when interacting with a controlled machine have been a matter of research investigation in various domains, from aerospace to semi-autonomous driving and robotics. Human-robot collaboration is one of the most exciting scenarios of application in which a continuous physical interaction between humans and the controlled plant is present. In this context, the human subject can adapt its control behavior to the external sensed dynamics. This capability has a significant observable effect on the control delay, making its characterization and prevision a crucial aspect to understand. This work investigates a linear modeling approach that uniquely describes human and robot control actions and applies to a collaborative robotic task.

I. HUMAN-IN-THE-LOOP CONTROL

In complex human-robot collaboration scenarios characterized by a continuous physical interaction, the analysis of human behavior and control action is crucial to investigate as a base to build any predictive technique. Modeling the human control action when interacting with a controlled machine has become almost an independent research field, involving multiple disciplines and approaches over the years. In this work, a linear control modeling technique is investigated and applied to human-robot interaction, focusing on the identification of human reactive delay in a collaborative task.

The underlying mathematical representation for human control action should be the same used to describe a linear servomechanism [1]. Specifically, a set of linear differential equations with constant coefficients, or equivalently, a transfer function in the frequency domain. In 1965, McRuer et al. in [2] introduced the most famous example that follows such an approach. The model foresaw an integrator and a simple delay element to model the human operator adaptation during the interaction with the machine. Here, the human action was studied with different controlled elements and represented a quasi-linear describing function.

Research in this direction in the robotics domain often investigates the exploitation of collaborative robot applications using virtual environments. In [3] for example, a neuroadaptive controller is used in a collaborative application with a robotic arm to analyze the human control action. The target point was shown in a virtual environment and randomly changed for each trial. While in [4], a similar virtual setup was combined with a haptic device. The identified human control parameters were the input of a human intention estimator, able to adapt

the impedance of the controlled device according to human actions.

However, these approaches do not investigate the effect of the learning process of external dynamics on human control delay. The classical quasi-linear model is the most suitable approach for this while focusing on the description of physiological background processes [4] [5] [6]. The crossover model has been used many times in literature for this purpose in the aeronautic domain, characterized by a high range of frequency which facilitates a frequency-domain analysis of the model.

The present work describes and applies such a modeling approach to different human-robot collaboration scenarios using a time-domain approach. The paper will be structured as follows: in the second section, the model theoretical background will be described in detail; in the third section it will be presented the proposed application scenario; in the fourth section, the obtained results will be analyzed and discussed; and in the final section will be illustrated the system identification process implemented in simulation.

II. QUASI-LINEAR HUMAN MODEL

It can be stated that the Crossover model expresses the behavioral invariance of the human in its effort to adapt to the controlled plant's dynamics, offering a consistent human-machine behavior where the functional block diagram can be described as a simple compensatory manual control system as shown in Figure 1.

For such a control structure, $r(s)$ is the Cartesian position goal, internally decided by the user that exerts a force towards the controlled element. Therefore, the external force applied by the human can be considered as the input of the controlled element $P(s)$, determining the output actual position $y(s)$ of the human-machine complex.

The crossover frequency is mainly dependent on human adaptation to the controlled element, and in a minor way, to the input bandwidth ω_i . Therefore, if we try to include the controlled element dynamics into the Precision model introduced in [7], we will have that the man-machine complex would be equivalent to

$$H(s)P(s) = K_{pc} \frac{\tau_{LC}s + 1}{\tau_{IC}s + 1} \frac{1}{\tau_n s + 1} e^{-s\tau_e} \quad (1)$$

Here, τ_{LC} and τ_{IC} are the lead-lag equalization parameters considered after the initial training phase, when the human

Fig. 1: Block scheme representing the structure of human-robot control system during a compensatory task, as described by the Crossover Model

learned the controlled machine dynamics and adapted its behavior to respect the crossover hypothesis. The gain K_{pc} is now a general expression of the gain of the man-machine transfer function and is equivalent to the crossover frequency.

The effective time delay τ_e results from transport delays of the sensory information to the central nervous system and high-frequency neuromuscular dynamics. In [8], it was given the following empirical relationship:

$$\tau_e = \tau_0 - \Delta\tau(\omega_i) \quad (2)$$

Here, the first term τ_0 is the primary time delay when $\omega_i = 0$, depends on the controlled element Y_c . In contrast, the second term decreases the effective delay with the input bandwidth with a slope entirely independent of the controlled element. However, a constant behavior is expected if we focus on the primary delay term dependent on human adaptation to the controlled external dynamics.

Therefore, the reaction time delay should be constant for each human subject, with a small variability attributable to task and environmental variables. In particular, typical values of 0.5s of the primary time delay τ_0 were obtained in [7] for second-order functions of the controlled element.

In this work, the Precision human-machine model has been applied to a human-robot collaboration scenario to understand how to identify better human control characteristics concerning its adaptation to the controlled robot's dynamics.

III. DESIGN OF EXPERIMENT

A simple manual guidance situation was considered, where humans and robots performed a typical point-to-point motion task with continuous physical interaction. In this scenario, the reactive delay can be derived from the time displacement between the reference position signal and the actual measured position.

Here, the reference signal to consider as the input $r(s)$ in Figure 1 is composed of a sum of steps being the series mentioned above of constant reference target points.

Figure 2 shows the position error derivative signal $\dot{e}(t)$ during a performed point-to-point task, being $e(t) = r(t) - p(t)$ the position error, $r(t)$ the reference position, and $p(t)$ the actual position. As noticeable, $\dot{e}(t)$ is characterized by a series of local maxima, represented by the orange crosses. Each maximum corresponds to the time frame for the maximum

Fig. 2: Time derivative of the position error signal in a performed experiment. Orange crosses represent local maxima, while green dots the first successive time instant where a sign change is observable.

Fig. 3: Scheme of the experimental setup: the disturbance signal causes a displacement from the initial reference position, and the human reacts by exerting a compensatory force towards the opposite direction.

variation in the reference position signal $r(t)$, *i.e.*, corresponding to a target point variation, as will be better detailed in the next section. The green dots represent the following time instant in which the considered error derivative becomes negative, caused by a variation in the actual position $p(t)$ in consequence of the human control action. Therefore, the difference between these two points can be considered a reliable experimental measure of the reactive time delay of the subject.

A cartesian impedance controller was implemented on the robot side, depicted as the controlled element $P(s)$ in Figure

1.

The proposed experimental setup, represented in Figure 3, consisted of a UR5 robotic arm with a gripper in the end-effector, which the operator must hold. A virtual model of the robot arm was shown on a screen to the human operator using the Rviz software tool. The reference target area, represented by a red square of 2cm in such a virtual environment, was shown. Its position was randomly changed in the x-y plane (in the robot's base frame). The human operator was asked to reach the target point by manually guiding the robot gripper, holding it for $\Delta t = 3s$, and bringing the robot back to the initial position. If the subject could not hold the robot end-effector within the reference target area for 3s, the counter was reset, and the following virtual reference was not generated until the condition mentioned above was respected.

This operation was continuously repeated with different target points for 60 seconds. Each experiment was performed ten times by ten different human subjects with the same series of random target values. Before recording the experiments, a training phase was performed by executing the described operations until a high level of comfort with the environment was reached and confirmed by the subject.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The recorded signals included many step motions since the human subject's reaction in both directions was considered when reaching the random target reference and returning to the initial position. The number of generated references depends on the subject's reaction delay and the precision when holding the robot into the target area. The total number of generated virtual references for each subject is indicated in the second row of Table ??, ranging from a minimum of 122 to a maximum of 151, considering all the ten performed experimental trials.

Fig. 4: Ranges of variation of mean reaction delay values considering the 10 performed experimental trials, for each human subject

Figure 4 shows a box and whiskers plot representing the range of variation of the measured reaction time delay for each human subject. Here, the vertical axis represents seconds. The mean value for each experiment of 60 seconds was computed to have a robust measure of such value. Then the series of

10 mean values per subject were considered, and the resulting mean delays are summarized in Table ??.

As noticeable, only two outliers are present in all the measured values. Instead, most subjects display a narrow range distributed around the mean values, describing a constant delay around all the experiments. Moreover, such constant mean values significantly differ between one subject and another, confirming what was expected from the theoretical models.

In three cases, the ranges of values presented more consistent variations to the majority. However, rather than being dependent on environmental or task variables, such behavior can be explained as an effect of the subject training and better adaptation to the external dynamics.

The range of variation of the measured delays is between 0.4 and 0.6 s, which is compatible with the values obtained by the model. Further details will be given in the following section.

V. SYSTEM IDENTIFICATION

The experimental data from all the subjects were compared with the simulated Man-Machine Precision Model results, as expressed in Equation 1. The considered human model is constituted by five parameters: the gain element K_{pc} , time constants τ_{LC} , τ_{IC} and τ_n , the effective time delay τ_e ; each one having a different influence on the model simulated output. The static gain is responsible for the crossover frequency value, and the time constants give the model response the typical second-order characteristics. In contrast, the effective time delay is the actual output parameter of interest to be compared with the measured values to check the model precision.

The same reference position signal, recorded from the performed experimental trials, was used as input of the simulated system, whose transfer function was implemented using the python control system library. Being $\hat{p}(t)$ the simulated time forced response of the model, we will have a prediction error

$$\hat{e}(t) = p(t) - \hat{p}(t) \quad (3)$$

Where $p(t)$ is the actual position recorded from the experiments, representing the ground truth in this case. For each simulated response, the following Prediction Performance Index (PPI) was defined:

$$PPI = \int_0^{t_s} |\hat{e}(t)| \quad (4)$$

Here, the integral of the error modulus was computed within the time window between 0 and t_s , which corresponds to the maximum simulated time frame.

The five parameters were varied within reasonable intervals. Specifically, we used 0-10 Hz for the crossover frequency, 0-2 seconds for the three-time constants, and 0-1 second for the effective time delay τ_e . The simulation was run for each value of the five parameters until the minimum prediction performance index was reached.

TABLE I: Parameters of the human control model as defined in Equation ?? which resulted to optimize the Prediction Performance Index in the performed simulations. All the values are expressed as an average between the 10 performed experiments for all the human subjects. The last row reports the experimentally obtained effective delay τ_e to be compared with the simulated ones.

Human Subject	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Crossover Frequency	2.13	2.367	2.249	2.452	2.245	2.037	2.45	2.134	2.519	1.914
τ_N	1.46	1.34	1.384	1.151	1.427	1.594	1.29	1.548	1.252	1.905
τ_{LC}	0.86	0.912	0.865	0.908	0.877	0.871	0.89	0.818	0.947	0.741
τ_{IC}	0.996	0.994	0.991	0.991	0.991	0.996	0.99	0.995	0.996	1
Simulated delay τ_e	0.511	0.351	0.417	0.331	0.415	0.541	0.366	0.53	0.32	0.7
Measured delay τ_e	0.6234	0.4075	0.4777	0.4308	0.446	0.626	0.4494	0.5701	0.4086	0.6469

Fig. 5: Simulated position outputs considering: the identified precision model (in green), standard CO Model (dashed orange line), and measured position output (in blue).

The results are summarized in Table I, where the average values of the ten experimental trials for each subject are reported for all the considered parameters. The crossover frequency of the model is generally set around 2-2.5 Hz, confirming the low-frequency operational range of the model. In the last row of the table, the measured reaction delays obtained from the experiments are reported. Comparing these values with the simulated reaction delays reported in the previous row, we can observe an error below 0.1s. This result confirms the match between the identified model and the data.

Another reliable indicator of the model accuracy is the comparison between the measured and simulated outputs, in our case, the actual position of the robot end-effector. Figure 5 compares the responses of the identified model (in green) and standard CO model (in orange), overlapped to the measured ground truth (in blue) recorded from the experiment, always considering the simulated parameters when the optimal PPI value has been reached. It is noticeable that, despite the good performances, CO model first-order characteristics fail to well represent the first peak observable at each step of the real system response.

On the other hand, the identified model response presents

these second-order characteristics observable in the experimental data due to its lead-lag equalization term. Moreover model response is completely overlapped with the measured one in the transient phase of each step, which is crucial for obtaining precise esteem of human reaction delay.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The linear approach of the proposed Precision model was able to accurately describe human-robot physical interaction during a compensatory control task.

The human effective reaction delay parameter was esteemed and extracted from raw post-process data to be reliable and invariant with task variables not dependent on the considered subject, confirming the model validity. Moreover, the system was identified by simulating a human-robot control model using the recorded experimental data, minimizing a performance index defined for this purpose. The simulated results corresponded with the experimental data for the computed effective delay and the raw position output.

Despite the encouraging results, some aspects will still have to be improved and more profoundly investigated: for instance, the human control model should be improved for an online human intention estimation to allow the controlled robot to update its control behavior accordingly during the task.

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